

WHAT IS MAN?

What is man? What is the defining characteristic mark of humankind? In the scheme of nature, what is the place—the distinctive place—of the human class of life? Have we propounded the question to ourselves? Professor Keyser thinks not, and in a brilliant address before the annual meeting of the Phi Beta Kappa Society at Columbia University discusses and expands a philosophy of life first sponsored by a Polish engineer, Count Alfred Korzybski.¹

Humans, he points out, entertain two concepts of man, inherited in the mesh of inherited opinions; the one biological or zoological; the other mythological. According to the zoological conception man is an animal, a conception having at least the merit of regarding humans as natural—a merit not possessed by the mythological conception which accords man no place in nature, he being neither natural nor supernatural, but a kind of miraculous union or hybrid of the two.

Are these conceptions true? Or rather since they can not both be true, is one of them true? It should not be amazing to find that both are false; for the concepts are man's and their object is man; thus the difficulty is unique; it is that of a self-conscious being having to regard its kind as an object and rightly conceiving what the object is. If they are not true what is the error in these traditional conceptions? The error is believed to lie in a confusion of types. Plants, the lowest order of living things, are classed as the basic-energy-binding or chemistry binding class of life, while the animals are the space binders—the space binding class of life. What now of human beings, who, like the animals, have the capacity for binding space but with no capacity of a higher order would indeed be animals? The difference lies in the power of initiative, of creative ability, of imagination or reason, the power that makes progress possible, a power not possessed by animals. By virtue of that familiar yet ever strange human power, each

generation inherits the fruit of the creative toil of bygone generations, augments the inheritance, and transmits it to the generations to come; then the dead survive in the living, destined with the living to greet and bless the yet unborn. Past, present, and future are not three; in man they are spiritually united to constitute one living reality and because this capacity for *binding time* under a law of ever-increasing amelioration is peculiar to man the class of human beings is to be conceived and scientifically defined to be the time-binding class of life. Not, as Professor Keyser points out, time binding animals, for time binding, chemistry binding, and space binding constitute three dimensions—three types of life to which belong man, plants and animals. Time-binding activity—the defining mark of man—may involve and often does involve space-binding as a higher involves a lower; but to say that, therefore, man is a species of animal—a time-binding species thereof—is like saying that a solid is a species of surface or that a violin is a species of wood or that symphony is a species of sound.

With this new conception of time binding, a study of man becomes the study of his time-binding energies; the laws of human nature are the natural laws of these energies. One of these laws is conceived as a law of perpetual growth and continued progress; a law of rapidly increasing geometric progression which reduces to the formula PR^{T-1} where P is the progress made in a given generation, R the ratio, and T the time. This then is the natural law for the advancement of civilization, only retarded in operation, the author believes, by the misconceptions man entertains of man, the misconception that man is but an animal and until man ceases to regard man as a species of animal the social life of the world and especially the ethical life will continue to be what it always has been in a large measure—zoological ethics.—
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¹ Keyser, Cassius J., *The Nature of Man*, Science, Vol. LIV, No. 1393, pp. 205-213, Friday, Sept. 9, 1921.